

O'ZBEKISTONDA MIGRATSIYANING HUQUQIY ASOSLARINI YARATILISHI**Muyiddinov Bekali Bahodir o'g'li**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Dunyo miqyosida e'tibor qaratilayotgan migratsiya masalasining tarixiy asoslarining yaratilishining yurtimizda qonuniy asoslari qay yo'sinda tashkil etilayotgani haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Yangi O'zbekiston, Fuqarolik va siyosiy huquqlar, modda, Migrantlar, chet el fuqarolari, qonun, Inson huquqlari umumjahon deklaratsiyasi, davlat organlari, Konstitutsiyaviy normalar, fuqarolar.

Yangi O'zbekistonning butun xalqaro hamjamiyatga ochiqlik siyosati mamlakat fuqarolari uchun erkin migratsiyaga keng imkoniyat yaratib berdi. Qolaversa, mamlakatimizga kelayotgan chet el fuqarolari uchun qulay huquqiy muhit yaratish maqsadida xalqaro standartlarga javob beruvchi migratsion nazorat tizimi va qonunchilik bazasi yaratildi.

Migratsiya sohasidagi davlat organlari faoliyatining asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri migratsiyaga doir qonunchilikni muvofiqlashtirish, inson huquqlari va qonuniy manfaatlarini himoyalash, davlat suverenitetini mustahkamlash va noqonuniy migratsiyaga qarshi kurashish hisoblanadi. O'zbekistonda migratsiya sohasida turizmni rivojlantirish, mehnat-migrantlarimizni ijtimoiy himoyalash, chet el fuqarolarining mamlakatimizda mehnat qilishi va vatandoshlarimizni tarixiy vataniga qaytishi uchun bir qator ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Koronavirus pandemiyasi tufayli yuzaga kelgan vaziyat fuqarolarimizning huquqlari va qonuniy manfaatlarini himoyalash sohasida xalqaro hamkorlikni kuchaytirish, ushbu yo'nalishda muvofiqlashtirilgan chora-tadbirlarni ko'rish, jumladan xorijiy davlatlarning vakolatli organlari bilan migratsiyadagi shaxslarga doir ma'lumotlarning tezkor almashinuvini yo'lga qo'yish zaruratini yana bir marotaba taqozo etdi. Odatda, migratsiya huquqining mazmun-mohiyati bir qancha huquqiy pog'onalarga taalluqli prinsiplar orqali ifodalanadi.

Konstitutsiyaviy normalarda mustahkamlangan ushbu huquq shaxsning konstitutsiyaviy huquqiy maqomining ustuvor manbalari hisoblanadigan 1948-yildagi Inson huquqlari umumjahon deklaratsiyasi, 1966-yildagi Fuqarolik va siyosiy huquqlar to'g'risidagi xalqaro paktga to'la muvofiq keladi. Mazkur huquqning e'tirof etilganligi va kafolatlaganligi nafaqat mamlakatimiz uchun, balki uning dunyo hamjamiyatiga integratsiyalashuvi nuqtai nazaridan yurtimizga keladigan migrantlar uchun ham ahamiyatlidir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasining 22-moddasiga muvofiq, O'zbekiston Respublikasi o'z hududida ham, uning tashqarisida ham o'z fuqarolarini huquqiy himoya qilish va ularga homiylik ko'rsatishni kafolatlaydi.

Shu bilan birga Konstitutsiyaning 23-moddasida O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududidagi chet el fuqarolarining va fuqaroligi bo'lmagan shaxslarning huquq va erkinliklari xalqaro huquq normalariga muvofiq ta'minlanishi, shuningdek ular O'zbekiston Respublikasining Konstitutsiyasi, qonunlari va xalqaro shartnomalari bilan belgilangan burchlarni ado etishlari mustahkamlangan.

hududida bir joydan ikkinchi joyga ko'chish, O'zbekiston Respublikasiga kelish va undan chiqib ketish huquqiga ega, deb ta'kidlanadi. Mazkur qoida Inson huquqlari Umumjahon Deklaratsiyasining 13-moddasi mazmuniga muvofiq ravishda tuzilgan.

Unda ta'kidlanishicha, birinchidan, har bir inson har bir davlat doirasida erkin yurish va yashash joyi tanlash huquqiga ega, ikkinchidan, har bir inson har qanday mamlakatdan, xususan o'z mamlakatidan chiqib ketish va o'z mamlakatiga qaytib kelish huquqiga ega. Shu tariqa O'zbekiston Konstitutsiyasida migratsion jarayonlarining turli jihatlari o'z aksini topgan.

Jumladan, migratsiya jarayonlarini tartibga solish, harakatlanish erkinligiga bo'lgan huquq asoslari mustahkamlangan. Konstitutsiyaviy normalar to'g'ridan-to'g'ri amal qilishi tufayli O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasining 44-moddasiga muvofiq, har bir shaxsga o'z huquq va erkinliklarini sud orqali himoya qilish, davlat organlari, mansabdor shaxslar, jamoat birlashmalarining g'ayriqonuniy xatti-harakatlari ustidan sudga shikoyat qilish huquqi kafolatlanadi. To'g'ridan-to'g'ri amal qilish huquqni qo'llash organlaridan qaror qabul qilayotib, avvalo, konstitutsiyaviy normaga va undan keyingina uni rivojlantirish uchun qabul qilingan qonunlar va boshqa normativ hujjatlarga havola qilishlarini talab etadi.

Migrantlarning inson huquqlarini himoyalash borasida xorij tajribasini ham o'rganish alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Jumladan, MDHning boshqa mamlakatlarida ham migratsiyaga oid konstitutsiyaviy normalarning qiyosiy tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, ushbu davlatlar fuqarolari xorijga chiqishlari, ayniqsa, qaytib kelishlarida to'siqsiz va istalgan payt erkin harakatlanishi, shu bilan birga, ushbu davlatlar hududidagi chet el fuqarolari va fuqaroligi bo'lmagan shaxslarning huquqiy maqomi aniq va ravshan belgilangan. Asosiy Qonunning 28-moddasiga ko'ra, "O'zbekiston Respublikasi fuqarosi Respublika hududida bir joydan ikkinchi joyga ko'chish, O'zbekiston Respublikasiga kelish va undan chiqib ketish huquqiga ega. Qonunda belgilangan cheklashlar bundan mustasnodir" deyilgan. Amaldagi tahrirda O'zbekiston hududida bir joydan ikkinchi joyga ko'chish, O'zbekiston Respublikasiga kelish va undan chiqib ketish kabi kategoriyalarning uchalasi ham istisno tarzida qonun bilan cheklanishi mumkin.

To'g'ridan-to'g'ri amal qilish huquqni qo'llash organlaridan qaror qabul qilayotib, avvalo, konstitutsiyaviy normaga va undan keyingina uni rivojlantirish uchun qabul qilingan qonunlar va boshqa normativ hujjatlarga havola qilishlarini talab etadi.

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